

CityGML 3.0 Vegetation ADE Proposal

Technical User Guide

The document at hand provides guidance on the use of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) CityGML 3.0 Conceptual Model (CM) and the proposed Vegetation Application Domain Extension (ADE).

This document supports the survey for the evaluation of the CityGML Vegetation ADE. The descriptions of the CityGML Conceptual Model (CM) and the proposed ADE have been simplified to retain essential information while reducing complexity. This approach ensures that even those unfamiliar with the standard can understand the content, benefit from it, and contribute to enhancing the Vegetation ADE.

The document at hand is a non-normative resource and not an official position of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC).

Except for the CityGML Vegetation ADE proposal, all the information provided in this document is retrieved from the official CityGML documentation:

- [OGC City Geography Markup Language \(CityGML\) 3.0 Conceptual Model Users Guide](#);
- [OGC City Geography Markup Language \(CityGML\) Part 1: Conceptual Model Standard](#).

The proposed CityGML Vegetation ADE is subject to change.

If you have questions or remarks about CityGML CM or the proposed Vegetation ADE, which are not addressed within this document, please feel free to use the following contacts:

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1 CityGML Conceptual Model

CityGML is an open standard that defines a conceptual model and exchange format for the representation, storage, and exchange of virtual 3D models of cities and landscapes, including 3D urban objects. It facilitates urban data sharing and semantic information in addition to geometric representation.

The CityGML 3.0 conceptual model is thematically decomposed into one Core module and 16 extension modules (Figure 1).

Figure 1: CityGML 3.0 Module overview. The vertical boxes show the different thematic modules. Horizontal modules specify concepts that are applicable to all thematic modules. Source: <https://docs.ogc.org/is/20-010/20-010.html#toc20>

The CityGML 3.0 standard is based on the ISO 191xx standards.

1.1 CityGML Vegetation Module

The CityGML Vegetation module facilitates the representation of vegetation objects within city models based on specific thematic classes.

Vegetation can be represented either as solitary vegetation objects, such as trees, bushes or as vegetation areas covered by plants of a given species or as a mixture of plant species, such as forests, meadows or steppes.

The CityGML 3.0 Vegetation module provides an abstract superclass for all vegetation objects called `AbstractVegetationObject`.

Furthermore, the solitary vegetation objects and the vegetation areas are represented by the following classes (Figure 2):

1. `SolitaryVegetationObject` represents individual vegetation objects not part of a continuous vegetation area, such as single trees or bushes.
2. `PlantCover` represents continuous vegetation areas, such as lawns, meadows, or forest patches.

Figure 2: CityGML Vegetation Module Interpretation. Source: L.M., adapted from: <https://3dcitydb-docs.readthedocs.io/en/release-v4.1/3dcitydb/uml/thematic-model/vegetation.html>

The UML model of the top-level feature types SolitaryVegetationObject and PlantCover is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: CityGML 3.0 Vegetation Module UML Diagram. Source: <https://3dcitydb-docs.readthedocs.io/en/release-v4.1/3dcitydb/uml/index.html>

1.2 CityGML Application Domain Extension (ADE)

Compared to buildings, vegetation objects are, to date, still very simplified and underrepresented in the CityGML standard. The Vegetation ADE for the CityGML 3.0 CM is proposed to tackle this shortcoming.

An Application Domain Extension (ADE) is a mechanism for customizing the CityGML CM and addressing the requirements of diverse applications related to, e.g. urban planning, infrastructure management, and environmental modelling.

ADEs support the development of formal and systematic extensions to the CityGML CM for specific applications or domains. They are used to model and exchange domain-specific information and to describe objects and properties that the CityGML CM does not directly support.

ADEs extend the CityGML CM by defining new feature types appropriate to the application area and additional content, such as object types, data types, code lists, and enumerations. This could encompass additional characteristics e.g. of buildings (e.g. energy consumption, construction material, etc.), transport (e.g., traffic density, speed limit, etc.), and other features. These extensions are typically developed by domain experts and standardization bodies to ensure consistency and interoperability across different applications.

1.3 CityGML Dynamizer

The previous version of CityGML, CityGML 2.0, was limited in modelling of dynamic data —data that change over time, such as energy consumption of buildings or (real-time) sensor measurements of environmental conditions. To overcome this shortcoming, the Dynamizer Module is introduced in the new version of the standard, CityGML 3.0, which is primarily used to integrate timeseries data for individual attributes of CityGML features. This is particularly important for representing phenomena that change over time. In the Vegetation ADE proposal, the Dynamizer Module finds application where dynamic characteristics, like vegetation growth, vegetation management and other dynamic processes need to be modelled for improved representation of urban environments.

The Dynamizer Module extends the existing CityGML features without altering the core structure of the CityGML model. This means that static features like trees can have attached Dynamizers that store or reference dynamic data. It can be used to inject dynamic variations of city object properties into an otherwise static representation.

The Dynamizer module supports the injection of timeseries data for individual attributes of CityGML features. Timeseries data can either be retrieved from external Sensor APIs (e.g. OGC SensorThings API, OGC Sensor Observation Services, MQTT, proprietary platforms), external standardized timeseries files (e.g. OGC TimeseriesML or OGC Observations & Measurements), external tabulated files (e.g. CSV) or can be represented inline as basic time-value pairs.

2 CityGML Glossary and most relevant terms

To keep our CityGML Vegetation ADE technical guide comprehensive, the CityGML concepts, terms, etc., which are not used in the proposed Vegetation ADE at hand, are not explained.

The full list of the CityGML Glossary, including the sources for its definition, can be found here: <https://docs.ogc.org/is/20-010/20-010.html#toc94>.

2.1 General

AbstractFeatureWithLifespan	A base class for all CityGML features. This class allows the optional specification of the real-world and database times for the existence of each feature.
Class	A category or type of city object that represents a specific kind of entity within a city model.
Feature	An abstraction of a real-world phenomenon.
Feature attribute	A characteristic of a feature.
Measurement	The act or result of determining the value of a property or characteristic of a feature.
Model	An abstraction of some aspects of reality. In CityGML, a digital representation of an urban environment that includes not just the geometry of physical objects but also their semantic, topological, and thematic properties.
Observation	The act of measuring or otherwise determining the value of a feature's property. This can result in one or more measurements.
Observation procedure	A method, algorithm, instrument, system or combination of these, which is used to make an observation.
Observation result	An estimate of the value of a property determined through a known observation procedure.

2.2 ISO Concepts

Boolean	A data type that represents a binary condition with only two possible values: true or false. It is used to indicate the presence or absence of a feature, the state of an object, or to specify whether a certain condition is met. For example, a Boolean value might be used to determine if a tree has a protection status (true) or not (false).
Character	A symbol from a standard character set.
CharacterString	A data type is used to denote a sequence of characters.
Date	A data type that represents a specific point in time. The date gives values for year, month and day. Representation of Date is specified in

ISO 8601. Principles for date and time are further discussed in ISO 19108.

Distance	A quantitative measure of the space or interval between two locations or objects.
Integer	A data type that represents an exact integer value (whole number) with no fractional parts or decimal components.
Length	A measure of the extent of an object or distance between two points in space is given as an integral.
Measure	The result of performing the act or process of ascertaining the extent, dimensions, or quantity of some entity.
UnitOfMeasure	Any system devised to measure some physical quantity such as distance, volume or area, or a system devised to measure such as the passage of time.
Uniform Resource Identifier (URI)	Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) is a compact string of characters used to identify or name a resource. It is a sequence of characters used to uniquely identify a resource or a piece of information on the internet or within a specific namespace.

2.3 Stereotypes

The following stereotypes are defined in the CityGML CM and are employed for the development of the proposed Vegetation ADE.

The stereotype is used in the CityGML CM only for classes that are imported from the ISO standards 19107, 19109, 19111, and 19123.

Application schema	A conceptual schema for data required by one or more applications.
CodeList	<p>Enumerates the valid attribute values. In contrast to Enumeration, the list of values is open and, thus, not given inline in the CityGML UML Model. The allowed values can be provided within an external code list.</p> <p><i>Code list values:</i> A code list is a form of enumeration where the valid values are defined in a separate register. The code list values consist of a link or identifier for the register as well as the value from that register which is being used.</p>
Data Type	Defines a set of properties that lack identity. A data type is a classifier with no operations whose primary purpose is to hold information.
ObjectType	Represents objects that have an identity but are not features.

FeatureType	Represents features that are similar and exhibit common characteristics. Features are abstractions of real-world phenomena and have an identity.
TopLevelFeatureType	Denotes features that represent the main components of the conceptual model. Top-level features may be further semantically and spatially decomposed and sub-structured into parts.
Property	Denotes attributes and association roles. This stereotype does not add further semantics to the conceptual model but is required to be able to add tagged values to the attributes and association roles that are relevant to the encoding.
Version	Denotes that the value of an association role that ends at a feature type is a specific version of the feature, not the feature in general.
Enumeration	Enumerates the valid attribute values in a fixed list of named literal values. Enumerations are specified in the CityGML CM.

2.4 UML Diagram

UML (Unified Modeling Language) diagrams are used to visually represent the CityGML CM. UML diagrams support documenting, understanding, and communicating the classes and their relationships.

UML is used for the definition of the proposed CityGML Vegetation ADE as it is prescribed by the OGC (see Figure 4).

The following colouring scheme is applied:

Classes painted in yellow are requirement classes already existing in the CityGML CM but are subject to discussion.

Classes painted in blue belong to requirements classes different to that associated with the yellow color.

Classes painted in orange are the proposed extensions of the CityGML Vegetation ADE.

The UML diagram of the CityGML Vegetation ADE (Figure 4) represents the existing CityGML Vegetation Modules (yellow and blue) alongside the newly proposed classes with their attributes (orange).

Additional attributes are also proposed for the existing FeatureTypes SolitaryVegetationObject and PlantCover. For instance, the SolitaryVegetationObject is proposed to have new attributes like age, dateOfExtermination or ecosystemService, etc.

Each attribute has a data type (type of value) and a multiplicity.

The data type can be, e.g. an Integer, a Date, a Measure, a Boolean, an Enumeration, a CodeList or a DataType.

The multiplicity is presented by bracketed numbers following attribute names, indicating how many instances of a particular feature type can be associated with another feature type or property.

[1] = exactly one

[0..*] = Zero or more

[0..1] = Optional – zero or one

[1..*] = one or more

3 CityGML Vegetation Module and ADE: UML Diagram

Figure 4: CityGML Vegetation Module and ADE Proposal - UML Diagram

4 Attribute Lists

4.1 Attribute List of the CityGML Vegetation Module

4.1.1 AbstractVegetationObject

Table 1 Metadata of AbstractVegetationObject (FeatureType)

Definition:	AbstractVegetationObject is the abstract superclass for all kinds of vegetation objects.
Subclass of:	AbstractOccupiedSpace
Stereotype:	«FeatureType»

4.1.2 SolitaryVegetationObject

Table 2 Metadata of SolitaryVegetationObject (TopLevelFeatureType)

Definition:	A SolitaryVegetationObject represents individual vegetation objects, e.g. trees or bushes.
Subclass of:	<u>AbstractVegetationObject</u>
Stereotype:	«TopLevelFeatureType»

NOTE: Unless otherwise specified, all attributes and role names have the stereotype «Property».

Table 3 Attributes of SolitaryVegetationObject (TopLevelFeatureType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
ADEOfSolitaryVegetationObject	<u>ADEOfSolitaryVegetationObject</u> [0..*]	Augments the SolitaryVegetationObject with properties defined in an ADE.
class	<u>SolitaryVegetationObjectClassValue</u> [0..1]	Indicates the specific type of the SolitaryVegetationObject.
function	<u>SolitaryVegetationObjectFunctionValue</u> [0..*]	Specifies the intended purposes of the SolitaryVegetationObject.
usage	<u>SolitaryVegetationObjectUsageValue</u> [0..*]	Specifies the actual uses of the SolitaryVegetationObject.
species	<u>SpeciesValue</u> [0..1]	Indicates the botanical name of the SolitaryVegetationObject.
crownDiameter	<u>Length</u> [0..1]	Specifies the diameter of the SolitaryCityObject's crown.

height	<u>Length</u> [0..1]	Distance between the highest point of the vegetation object and the lowest point of the terrain at the bottom of the object.
maxRootBallDepth	<u>Length</u> [0..1]	Specifies the vertical distance between the lowest point of the SolitaryVegetationObject's root ball and the terrain surface.
rootBallDiameter	<u>Length</u> [0..1]	Specifies the diameter of the SolitaryCityObject's root ball.
trunkDiameter	<u>Length</u> [0..1]	Specifies the diameter of the SolitaryCityObject's trunk.

4.1.3 PlantCover

Table 4 Metadata of PlantCover (TopLevelFeatureType)

Definition:	A PlantCover represents a space covered by vegetation.
Subclass of:	<u>AbstractVegetationObject</u>
Stereotype:	«TopLevelFeatureType»

Table 5 Attributes of PlantCover (TopLevelFeatureType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
ADEOfPlantCover	<u>ADEOfPlantCover</u> [0..*]	Augments the PlantCover with properties defined in an ADE.
averageHeight	<u>Length</u> [0..1]	Specifies the average height of the PlantCover.
class	<u>PlantCoverClassValue</u> [0..1]	Indicates the specific type of the PlantCover.
function	<u>PlantCoverFunctionValue</u> [0..*]	Specifies the intended purposes of the PlantCover
maxHeight	<u>Length</u> [0..1]	Specifies the maximum height of the PlantCover
minHeight	<u>Length</u> [0..1]	Specifies the minimum height of the PlantCover.
usage	<u>PlantCoverUsageValue</u> [0..*]	Specifies the actual uses of the PlantCover.

4.2 Attribute List of CityGML Vegetation ADE Proposal

4.2.1 SolitaryVegetationObject

The ADE does not change the SolitaryVegetationObject class, it only adds further properties.

4.2.2 ADEOfSolitaryVegetationObject

The new properties of SolitaryVegetationObject are added to a new subclass of the data type ADEOfSolitaryVegetationObject with the stereotype «DataType».

NOTE: Unless otherwise specified, all attributes and role names have the stereotype «Property».

4.2.3 SolitaryVegetationObjectProperties

Table 6 Metadata of SolitaryVegetationObjectProperties (DataType)

Definition:	A SolitaryVegetationObjectProperties represents new properties of SolitaryVegetationObject added to the subclass ADEOfSolitaryVegetationObject.
Subclass of:	ADEOfSolitaryVegetationObject
Stereotype:	«DataType»

Table 7 Attributes of SolitaryVegetationObjectProperties (DataType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
age	Integer [0..1]	Specifies the age in years of the SolitaryVegetationObject.
dateOfExtermination	Date [0..1]	Specifies the date that a SolitaryVegetationObject has been cut down, removed or died.
dateOfPlanting	Date [0..1]	Specifies the planting date of the SolitaryVegetationObject on this site.
ecosystemService	EcosystemServiceValue [0..*]	Specifies the ecosystem services which are especially supported.
ownership	OwnershipTypeValue [0..1]	Categorizes the ownership status or entity responsible for the management and maintenance of the SolitaryVegetationObject.
protectionStatus	Boolean [0..1]	The protection status provides information about the protection status of the SolitaryVegetationObject (true or false).
seasonalChange	SeasonalChange [0..*]	Defines the type of morphological visible changes that a SolitaryVegetationObject is undergoing due

		to seasonal transitions as well as the start and end dates.
significance	SignificanceTypeValue [0..*]	The significance attribute refers to the importance of a given s SolitaryVegetationObject relevant to the corresponding environment. SolitaryVegetationObject may be associated e.g. with historical events, figures, or timelines, such memorial trees, trees at historical landmarks, or ancient trees.
speciesClassification	SolitaryVegetationObjectClassification [0..1]	Specifies the classification of a SolitaryVegetationObject (e.g. tree or bush) at the species level, according to a referenced classification system and a popular name.

Table 8 Attributes of SolitaryVegetationObjectClassification (DataType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
classificationName	CharacterString [0..*]	Specifies the name of the referenced classification system to define the SolitaryVegetationObject.
classificationReference	URI [0..1]	Provides a URI for the referenced classification system.
classificationCode	CharacterString [0..*]	Specifies the code within the referenced classification system corresponding to the SolitaryVegetationObject at a species level. It's a part of the scientific naming convention binomial nomenclature, where organisms are designated by their genus followed by their species identifier. This classification is used universally by scientists to ensure clear communication and understanding about a particular organism without ambiguity.
speciesPopularName	CharacterString [0..*]	Defines the popular name(s) of the SolitaryVegetationObject's species.

Table 9 Attributes of SeasonalChange (DataType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
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seasonalChangeType	SeasonalChangeTypeValue [0..1]	Defines the type of morphological visible changes that a SolitaryVegetationObject is undergoing due to seasonal transitions.
startDate	Date [0..1]	Defines the date when the seasonal change defined with SeasonalChangeTypeValue begins.
endDate	Date [0..1]	Defines the date when the seasonal change defined with SeasonalChangeTypeValue ends.

4.2.3.1 Crown

Table 10 Attributes of Crown (FeatureType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
crownClearance	Measure [0..1]	Describes the vertical distance from the ground to the point where the crown of a tree begins. It is, amongst others, used to calculate crown volume together with tree height and crown diameter. Crown clearance is also known as clearance height, stem extent, "bole extent", tree bole height, or trunk height to the first branch.
crownDensity	Measure [0..1]	Defines the quantity of stems, branches, twigs, shoots, buds, foliage, and reproductive structures within a tree's crown that obstruct light from passing through. This includes both live and dead branches as well as dead tops. It is recorded as a percentage.
crownDiameter	Measure [0..1]	Defines the average diameter of the canopy of the SolitaryVegetationObject.
crownType	CrownTypeValue [0..1]	Defines the type of tree crown, also known as "tree crown form" in its natural shape. It is a fundamental characteristic of the overall shape of the tree crown, inherent to the respective tree species.
leafTexture	URI [0..1]	A link to a URI, providing a resource with the typical texture of the leaf. This facilitates the automatic visualization of the leaves.

4.2.3.2 Trunk

Table 11 Attributes of Trunk (FeatureType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
trunkDiameter	Measure [0..1]	Specifies the trunk diameter at breast height (DBH).
trunkHeight	Measure [0..1]	Specifies the average trunk height.
trunkType	TrunkTypeValue [0..1]	Defines the structural configuration and branching pattern of a tree's main stem or trunk. It classifies trunks into distinct categories based on the number and arrangement of primary trunks.
trunkTexture	URI [0..1]	A link to a URI, providing a resource with the typical texture of the trunk. This facilitates the visualization of the trunk.

4.2.3.3 Root

Table 12 Attributes of Root (FeatureType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
rootBallDiameter	Measure [0..1]	Specifies the average diameter of the root ball.
rootBallMaximalDepth	Measure [0..1]	Specifies the maximal root ball depth.
rootType	RootTypeValue [0..1]	Specifies the root type.

4.2.3.4 SolitaryVegetationObjectGrowth

Table 13 Attributes of SolitaryVegetationObjectGrowth (FeatureType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
growthType	PlantCoverGrowthTypeValue [0..1]	Indicates a dynamic attribute of the SolitaryVegetationObject which is monitored and measured.
growthValue	Measure [0..1]	Defines to the Measure for the indicated growthType.
healthStatus	HealthStatusValue [0..1]	Represents the health status of the SolitaryVegetationObject at the time of measurement or observation.

potentialHazard	PotentialHazardValue [0..1]	Specifies potential hazards associated with the SolitaryVegetationObject.
observationProcedure	ObservationProcedureValue [0..1]	Defines the method or procedure by which the Measure is obtained. It provides insight into how a particular set of data is derived or collected.

4.2.4 PlantCover

The ADE does not change the PlantCover class. It only adds further properties.

4.2.5 ADEOfPlantCover

The new properties of *PlantCover* are added to a new subclass of the data type *ADEOfPlantCover* with the stereotype «DataType».

NOTE: Unless otherwise specified, all attributes and role names have the stereotype «Property».

4.2.6 PlantCoverProperties

Table 14 Metadata of PlantCoverProperties (DataType)

Definition:	A PlantCoverProperties represents new properties of PlantCover added to the subclass ADEOfPlantCover.
Subclass of:	ADEOfPlantCover
Stereotype:	«DataType»

Table 15 Attributes of PlantCoverProperties (DataType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
plantCoverSpecies	PlantCoverSpeciesClassification [0..*]	Specifies the classifications of the species present in the PlantCover which are <u>not</u> listed as a SolitaryVegetationObject, e.g. different grasses, flowers or herbs growing on the PlantCover, at the species level according to the referenced classification system, popular name, as well as the species relative abundance.
dateOfExtermination	Date [0..1]	Specifies the date that a PlantCover has been cut down, removed or died.
dateOfPlanting	Date [0..1]	Specifies the planting date of the PlantCover on this site.
ecosystemService	EcosystemServiceValue [0..*]	Specifies the ecosystem services which are especially supported.
habitatClassification	HabitatClassificationSystem [0..1]	Defines the habitat classification system, which is used for the habitat classification, specifying which habitat represents the PlantCover.
ownership	OwnershipTypeValue [0..1]	Categorizes the ownership status or entity responsible for the management and maintenance of the PlantCover.

protectionStatus	Boolean [0..1]	Defines the protection status of the PlantCover (true or false).
seasonalChange	SeasonalChange [0..*]	Defines the type of morphological visible changes that the PlantCover is undergoing due to seasonal transitions as well as the start and end dates.
significance	SignificanceTypeValue [0..*]	Refers to the importance of a given PlantCover relevant to the corresponding environment. PlantCovers may be associated with e.g. historical events, figures, or timelines such as areas which are sites of historical events, ancient habitats, places of memorandum or old agricultural practices.
startHeightOfCanopy	Measure [0..1]	Specifies at which height the canopy of the PlantCover starts. It is especially relevant for e.g. forests.

Table 16 Attributes of PlantCoverClassificationSystem (DataType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
plantCoverClassificationName	CharacterString [0..*]	Specifies the name of the referenced plant classification system to define Plant Cover.
plantCoverClassificationReference	URI [0..1]	Provides a URI for the referenced plant cover classification system.
plantCoverClassificationCode	CharacterString [0..*]	Specifies the code within the referenced classification system corresponding to the PlantCover at a species level. It's a part of the scientific naming convention binomial nomenclature, where organisms are designated by their genus followed by their species identifier. This classification is used universally by scientists to ensure clear communication and understanding about a particular organism without ambiguity.
speciesPopularName	Character String [0..*]	Defines the popular name of the PlantCover species.
speciesTypeRelativeAbundance	Integer [0..1]	Specifies the relative abundance of the PlantCover's species. It is the proportion of

		individuals belonging to a specific species compared to the total number of individuals of all species in a defined community or area. It is calculated as follows: Relative Abundance (%) = (Number of individuals of one species / Total number of individuals of all species) * 100.
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Table 17 Attributes of HabitatClassificationSystem (DataType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
habitatClassificationName	CharacterString [0..*]	Specifies the name of the habitat classification system referenced for the habitat classification.
habitatClassificationReference	URI [0..1]	Specifies the URI of the referenced habitat classification system.
habitatClassificationCode	CharacterString [0..*]	Specifies habitat code of the referenced habitat classification system, which corresponds to the PlantCover object.

Table 18 Attributes of SeasonalChange (DataType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
seasonalChangeType	SeasonalChangeTypeValue [0..1]	A code list that enumerates the different types of seasonal changes of vegetation.
startDate	Date [0..1]	Defines the date when the seasonal change defined in SeasonalChangeTypeValue begins.
endDate	Date [0..1]	Defines the date when the seasonal change defined in SeasonalChangeTypeValue ends.

4.2.6.1 PlantCoverGrowth

Table 19 Attributes of PlantCoverGrowth (FeatureType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
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growthType	PlantCoverGrowthTypeValue [0..1]	Defines a dynamic attribute of the PlantCover object, which is monitored and measured.
growthValue	Measure [0..1]	Defines the Measure for the indicated growth.
healthStatus	HealthStatusValue [0..1]	Represents the health status of the PlantCover object at the time of measurement or observation.
potentialHazard	PotentialHazardValue [0..1]	Specifies potential hazards associated with the PlantCover Object.
observationProcedure	ObservationProcedureValue [0..1]	Defines the method or procedure by which the Measure is obtained. It provides insight into how a particular set of data is derived or collected.

4.3 VegetationManagement

Table 20 Attributes of VegetationManagement (FeatureType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
managementBody	ManagementBody [0..1]	Defines the management body responsible for the management of the vegetation.
managementType	ManagementTypeValue [0..*]	Defines how the vegetation is being managed and maintained.

Table 21 Attributes of ManagementBody (DataType)

Attribute	Value type and multiplicity	Definition
name	CharacterString [0..*]	Provides the name of the management body e.g. company name.
managementBodyType	Character String [0..*]	Defines the type of management body responsible for the vegetation.
address	CharacterString [0..*]	Defines the address of the management body.

5 CityGML Vegetation ADE Proposal: DataTypes

The new DataTypes for the Vegetation ADE are represented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: DataTypes of the CityGML 3.0 Vegetation ADE Proposal

6 CityGML Vegetation ADE Proposal: CodeLists

«CodeList» enumerates the valid attribute values. In contrast to “Enumeration”, the list of values is open and, thus, not given inline in the CityGML UML Model. The allowed values can also be provided within an external code list.

The newly defined CodeLists for the Vegetation ADE (Figure 6) are defined in the following tables.

Figure 6: CodeLists of the CityGML 3.0 Vegetation ADE Proposal

Table 22 Metadata of EcosystemServiceValue (CodeList)

Definition:	EcosystemServiceValue is a code list that enumerates the different types of ecosystem services a SolitaryVegetationObject or PlantCover can provide.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype	«CodeList»
Values	airQualityRegulation aestheticValue biodiversityMaintenance carbonSequestration climateRegulation cooling culturalService diseaseRegulation erosionControl fiberAndMaterialProduction foodProduction habitatProvision noiseReduction nutrientCycling otherProduction photosynthesisAndPrimaryProduction

	<p> pollination shading soilFormationAndFertility wasteDecompositionAndDetoxification waterCycle waterPurification waterRegulationAndManagement </p>
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Table 23 Metadata of ObservationProcedureValue (CodeList)

Definition:	ObservationProcedureValue is a code list that enumerates the different procedures, processes, methods, algorithms or instruments, or system of these, which may be used in making an observation to measuring or otherwise determining the value of a property – to obtain data.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype	«CodeList»
Values	<p> fieldSurvey aerialPhotography expertEstimation externalDataBase LiDAR multispectralAndHyperspectralImaging syntheticApertureRadar simulation calibratedSimulation sensor volunteeredGeographicInformation </p>

Table 24 Metadata of OwnershipTypeValue (CodeList)

Definition:	OwnershipTypeValue is a code list that enumerates ownership status or entity responsible for the governance and maintenance.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype	«CodeList»
Values:	<p> communityOrCollective indigenous institutional privatePublicHybrid privateResidential privateCommercial privateAgricultural publicFederal </p>

	publicMunicipal publicState
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Table 25 Metadata of PotentialHazardValue (CodeList)

Definition:	PotentialHazardValue is a code list that enumerates the different types of potential hazards of SolitaryVegetationObject and PlantCover.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype:	«CodeList»
Values:	allergenicPollen diseaseVectorHabitat encroachmentOnInfrastructure fallingBranches fireHazard interferenceWithInfrastructure invasiveSpecies LeafLitter nutrientDepletion obstructionOfVisibility poisonous punctureWounds rootIntrusion skinIrritation toxicBerries unstableVegetation waterContamination wildfireRisk windthrow

Table 26 Metadata of SeasonalChangeTypeValue (CodeList)

Definition:	SeasonalChangeTypeValue is a code list that enumerates the different types of seasonal changes of vegetation.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype:	«CodeList»
Values:	<p>growth leafEmergence floweringPeriod fruitAndSeedDevelopment seedDispersal leafSenescence leafShedding needleDrop retentionOfFoliage dormancy</p>

Table 27 Metadata of SignificanceTypeValue (CodeList)

Definition:	SignificanceTypeValue is a code list that enumerates the different types of significance.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype:	«CodeList»
Values:	<p>conservational cultural economical environmental global historical recreational spiritual</p>

Table 28 Metadata of CrownTypeValue (CodeList)

Definition:	CrownTypeValue is a code list that enumerates the different types of crowns of a SolitaryVegetationObject.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype:	«CodeList»
Values:	irregular conical cylindrical spherical elliptical ovate invertedOvate umbrellaShaped palmShaped weeping

Table 29 Metadata of TrunkTypeValue (CodeList)

Definition:	TrunkTypeValue is a code list that enumerates the different types of crowns of a SolitaryVegetationObject.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype:	«CodeList»
Values:	fallenTreeTrunk singleTrunk multipleTrunks banyanLikeTrunks

Table 30 Metadata of RootTypeValue (CodeList)

Definition:	RootTypeValue is a code list used to specify root types of the SolitaryVegetationObject.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype:	«CodeList»
Values:	taproot lateralRoot heartRoot tuberousRoot rhizome sinkerRoots

Table 31 Metadata of ManagementTypeValue (CodeList)

Definition:	ManagementTypeValue is a code list that enumerates the different types of management or care activities applied to a SolitaryVegetationObject or PlantCover.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype:	«CodeList»
Values:	brushRemoval canopyManagement diseaseAndPestControl diseaseAndPestMonitoring fertilisation grazingManagement hazardousTreeRemoval herbicides intensifiedUse invasiveSpeciesRemoval irrigationManagement managedForRecreation mulching prescribedBurning pruning speciesConservation soilAmendment treeBending wildlifeHabitatManagement

7 CityGML Vegetation ADE Proposal: Enumerations

The newly defined Enumerations for the CityGML Vegetation ADE (Figure 7) are defined in the following tables.

Figure 7: Enumerations of the CityGML 3.0 Vegetation ADE proposal

Table 32 Metadata of HealthStatusValue (Enumeration)

Definition:	HealthStatusValue is an enumeration that enumerates the different types of health states of vegetation. It is the same for SolitaryVegetationObject as for PlantCover.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype:	«Enumeration»
Values:	Excellent Good Fair Poor Critical Dead

Table 33 Metadata of SolitaryVegetationGrowthTypeValue (Enumeration)

Definition:	SolitaryVegetationObjectGrowthTypeValue is an enumeration that encompasses the different attributes used to describe a SolitaryVegetationObject's growth.
Subclass of:	SolitaryVegetationObjectProperties
Stereotype:	«Enumeration»
Values:	height crownClearance crownDensity crownDiameter trunkDiameter trunkHeight rootBallDiameter maxRootBallDepth

Table 34 Metadata of PlantCoverGrowthTypeValue (Enumeration)

Definition:	PlantCoverGrowthTypeValue is an enumeration that includes the different attributes used to describe a PlantCover's growth.
Subclass of:	PlantCoverProperties
Stereotype:	«Enumeration»
Values:	averageHeight minHeight maxHeight startHeightOfCanopy

Table 35 Metadata of UnitOfMeasure (Enumeration)

Definition:	UnitOfMeasure is an enumeration used to specify the unit of a measure.
Subclass of:	None
Stereotype:	«Enumeration»
Values:	cm m km in ft miles percentage

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